

and N-H bonds were indicated as usual. The rearrangement of the nitriles under the catalytic influence of bases is under study.

The addition compounds of the active methylene compounds with N- α -bromo cinnamylidene-*p*-toluidine which crystallized from benzene with their characteristics are listed in Table 2. The nature of these compounds is under study.

TABLE 2

Active methylene compound	m.p. °C	Product Yield %
1. Ethylcyanoacetate	185	85
2. Cyanoacetamide	125	78
3. Ethylmalonate	173	78
4. Malononitrile	225	78
5. Acetylacetone	168	70

The 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition compounds of benzonitrile oxide with N- α -bromocinnamylidene arylamines are listed on Table (3) and are under further study.

TABLE 3

Cycloadditions of benzonitrile

Conjugated imine :	Adduct : m.p.°C
1. N- α -Bromocinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -toluidine	222
2. N- α -Bromocinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	148
3. N- α -Bromocinnamylidene- <i>p</i> -phenetidine	160

TABLE 4

Reissert compounds

R.	Av.	m.p. °C	Yield %
1.H.	Phenyl	161	98
2.H.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	189	95
3.H.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	185	95
4.H.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	154	90
5.H.	<i>p</i> -Phenetyl	172	93
6.H.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	156	90
7.Br.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	156	96

The Reissert compounds (III) prepared from conjugated imines, by treatment with benzoyl chloride and potassium cyanide and crystallized from benzene, are listed in Table 4 with their characteristics. The behaviour of these open-chain Reissert nitriles which do not appear to have been reported earlier, on hydrolysis with acid and alkali, on reaction with aldehydes, imines, Grignard reagents, isocyanates and lithium compounds, is under study.